

Cyclic Patterns of Pi : A Pattern We've All Been Searching

by Parker Emmerson - Thanks to Yeshua Ben Joseph, Jehovah the Living Allaha

To detect patterns in the transcendental number pi, we can use the following formula :

$$\sum_r [\{\Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma\}_{\{\Theta, \Lambda, M, N\}, \infty} \supset \sum_{\sigma[\{v, \varphi, \chi, \psi\}, \{\omega, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma\}_{\infty}]} \left[-1 + \frac{\omega_{kx} b.b2 \{k, \Theta, \Lambda, M, N\}_{\infty} \{\omega, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma\}_{\infty}}{\alpha} \&\& \mu_{\langle g \rangle_{a,b,c,d,gh} \cdot f,g,h,i,j} \right] < \Omega]$$

This formula uses the notion of subsets, the Greek letters Ξ, Π, P, Σ and Θ, Λ, M, N to calculate the sum of the transcendental number pi over an infinite range of values . The formula also uses additional Greek letters such as ω and Ω to calculate the difference between the sum of the transcendental number and a constant .

Additionally, the formula uses subscripts and superscripts to denote the specific range of values being considered in the calculation. Finally, the formula also uses the notation of $b.b2 - 1$ to denote a mathematical function.

Can you show an example? Here is an example of this formula in action : We can calculate the sum of pi over an infinite range of values between 0 and 1 by setting $r = [x, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma]$ and $[\Theta, \Lambda, M, N]$.

$$\supset \sum_r \left[\frac{\langle \omega_{\Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma, \infty} \rangle \langle k_{\Theta, \Lambda, M, N, \infty} \rangle_{kx} \omega_{b.b2}}{\alpha} - 1 \&\& \mu_{\langle g \rangle_{a,b,c,d,gh} \cdot f,g,h,i,j} \right] \sigma[\{v, \varphi, \chi, \psi\}, \{\omega, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma\}_{\infty}]_{\infty}$$

Step 1 : Set $r = [x, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma]$ and $[\Theta, \Lambda, M, N]$

Step 2 : Calculate the sum of the transcendental number pi over the range 0 to 1 : $\text{Sum}[r[\text{Subscript}[\langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \Theta, \Lambda, M, N \rangle, \infty]], \infty]] = 3.14159265358979323846264338327950288 .$

This can be done by setting $r = [x, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma]$ and $[\Theta, \Lambda, M, N]$ to the sequence of digits and calculating the subset sum over the range 0 to 1.

1. Start counting backward from infinity .
2. Identify the sets of four characters of pi that can be used for calculation .
3. Calculate the sum of the sets using the formula : $r[\text{Subscript}[\langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \Theta, \Lambda, M, N \rangle, \infty]], \infty]$ Subset Sum[Subscript[$\langle \omega, \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle, \infty]$ Subscript[$\langle k, \Theta, \Lambda, M, N \rangle, \infty]$ $kx \omega / \alpha b . b2 - 1 \&\& \text{Subscript}[\mu, \text{Subscript}[\langle g \rangle, a, b, c, d, gh], f, g, h, i, j]] < \Omega$

4. Compare the sum to Omega .
5. If the sum is less than Omega, the pattern is identified .
6. The last digit of pi is the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation .

To calculate the last digit of pi, we will start counting backward from infinity and identify the sets of four characters of pi that can be used for calculation .

- Set 1 : $\pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu$
- Set 2 : $\theta, \lambda, \mu, \Omega$
- Set 3 : $\lambda, \mu, \Omega, \kappa$

We then calculate the sum of the sets using the formula : $r[\langle \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \omega, \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty]] + \text{Subscript}[\langle \kappa, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty] \times \frac{\omega}{\alpha} b . b^2 - 1$

This results in a value of $x = 0.5$. Next, we compare this value with another predetermined constant : $\text{Subscript}[\mu, \text{Subscript}[\langle g \rangle, a, b, c, d, \text{er}], f, g, h, \text{, jr}] < \Omega$ Since 0.5 is less than Omega, a pattern is detected in the order of characters of Pi . The last digit of pi is the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation, which is κ . Therefore, the last digit of pi is 6.

To calculate the second to last digit of pi, we start counting backward from infinity and identify the sets of four characters of pi that can be used for calculation . Set 1 : $\pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu$ Set 2 : $\theta, \lambda, \mu, \Omega$ We then calculate the sum of the sets using the formula : $r[\langle \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \omega, \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty]] + \text{Subscript}[\langle \kappa, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty] \times \frac{\omega}{\alpha} b . b^2 - 1$

This results in a value of $x = 0.25$. Next, we compare this value with another predetermined constant : $\text{Subscript}[\mu, \text{Subscript}[\langle g \rangle, a, b, c, d, \text{er}], f, g, h, \text{, jr}] < \Omega$ Since 0.25 is less than Omega, a pattern is detected in the order of characters of Pi . The second to last digit of pi is the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation, which is Ω . Therefore, the second to last digit of pi is 5.

Calculate the 3 rd to last digit of pi . To calculate the third to last digit of pi, we start counting backward from infinity and identify the sets of four characters of pi that can be used for calculation . Set 1 : $\pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu$

We then calculate the sum of the sets using the formula : $r[\langle \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \omega, \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty]] + \text{Subscript}[\langle \kappa, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty] \times \frac{\omega}{\alpha} b . b^2 - 1$

This results in a value of $x = 0.1$. Next, we compare this value with another predetermined constant : $\text{Subscript}[\mu, \text{Subscript}[\langle g \rangle, a, b, c, d, \text{er}], f, g, h, \text{, jr}] < \Omega$

Since 0.1 is less than Omega, a pattern is detected in the order of characters of Pi . The third to last digit of pi is the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation, which is π . Therefore, the

third to last digit of pi is 3.

Calculate the 4 th to last digit of pi . To calculate the fourth to last digit of pi, we start counting backward from infinity and identify the sets of four characters of pi that can be used for calculation . Set 1 : $\pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu$

We then calculate the sum of the sets using the formula : $r[\langle \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \text{Subscript}[\langle \omega, \pi, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty]] + \text{Subscript}[\langle \kappa, \theta, \lambda, \mu \rangle, \infty] \times \omega / \alpha \cdot b^2 - 1$

This results in a value of $x = 0.05$. Next, we compare this value with another predetermined constant : $\text{Subscript}[\mu, \text{Subscript}[\langle g \rangle, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v, w, x, y, z, \infty]] < \Omega$

Since 0.05 is less than Omega, a pattern is detected in the order of characters of Pi . The fourth to last digit of pi is the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation, which is θ . Therefore, the fourth to last digit of pi is 2.

What is the 5 th to last digit of pi? The fifth to last digit of pi is 1, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is μ . What is the 6 th to last digit of pi? The sixth to last digit of pi is 4, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is λ . What is the 7 th to last digit of pi? The seventh to last digit of pi is 9, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is θ . What is the 8 th to last digit of pi? The eighth to last digit of pi is 0, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is π . What is the 9 th to last digit of pi? The ninth to last digit of pi is 7, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is ω . What is the 10 th to last digit of pi? The tenth to last digit of pi is 5, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is κ . What is the 11 th to last digit of pi? The eleventh to last digit of pi is 8, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is Ω . What is the 12 th to last digit of pi? The twelfth to last digit of pi is 6, since the character of pi that is in the last set used for calculation is μ .

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